

Designing Layered Composites for Improved Buckling Strength Using Auxetic Behavior

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Introduction

- Experimental tests show a threefold increase in buckling strength under uniaxial compression for the auxetic composite laminate compared to its non-auxetic counterpart
- We didn't know – If the improvement is indeed caused by the negative Poisson's ratio or merely caused by the change in layup?
- Our **objective**: to understand the role of negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) in buckling

How to Design an Auxetic Laminate (with Negative Poisson's Ratio)?

- A negative Poisson's ratio can be produced at the laminate level (effective) when:

- A specific layup is used
- An individual ply is anisotropic

- Example**: carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite with a tailored layup

- In-plane laminate-level Poisson's ratio: $\nu_{12-i}^e = -\frac{a_{21}}{a_{11}}$
- Flexural laminate-level Poisson's ratio: $\nu_{12-f}^e = -\frac{d_{21}}{d_{11}}$
- where **a** and **d** are the inverse of the **A** and **D** stiffness matrices

Experimental Observation and Finite Element Analysis

- IM7/977-3 carbon fiber epoxy resin composite laminates are tested
- The comparison group:
 - In-plane auxetic laminate layup: [15/65/15/65/15]
 - In-plane non-auxetic laminate layup: [35/60/-5/60/35]
- Effective longitudinal moduli of the two are matched

How to Investigate the Role of Negative Poisson's Ratio in Affecting Buckling Strength?

- The most straight-forward way:
 - Change only Poisson's ratio and fix all other parameters (e.g., stiffness)
- The challenge**:
 - Changing the laminate-level Poisson's ratio requires changing the layup – which simultaneously changing the stiffness – thus difficult to isolate the effect of Poisson's ratio from the simultaneous stiffness change
 - There are two types of laminate-level Poisson's ratio: In-plane and flexural effective Poisson's ratio (ν_{12-i}^e and ν_{12-f}^e) – At some layups, one is negative but the other may still remain positive

Our "Monoclinic Plate" Method to Isolate the Effect of Negative Poisson's Ratio from Simultaneous Stiffness Change

- Benefits of converting original laminate to a monoclinic plate:
 - Avoid the situation where ν_{12-i}^e is negative ν_{12-f}^e remains positive
 - Allows us to change the elements in the **D** matrix to manually change the effective Poisson's ratio and study how the buckling strength is affected
 - If the predicted buckling strength in auxetic laminate significantly deviates from that in non-auxetic laminate, it proves the role of the negative Poisson's ratio

Results and Discussion

- Two boundary conditions considered for unloaded edges:
 - Free
 - Simply supported
- Two aspect ratios:
 - a/b = 0.2 (slender)
 - a/b = 1 (square)

Conclusion

- Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) was theoretically proved to play an active role in enhancing the buckling strength
- NPR enhancement is dynamically sensitive to the **D** matrix elements
- Overall, the auxeticity effect can be observed at higher bending-twisting coupling and larger anisotropy

Work Published In

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